

ISSN (o): 3030-3362

N^o 4(13)

IV. 2024

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
N^o 078777

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

- ✓ ANIQ FANLAR
- ✓ TABIIY FANLAR
- ✓ SIYOSIY FANLAR
- ✓ IJTIMOY FANLAR

- ✓ IQTISOD FANLARI
- ✓ TEXNIKA FANLARI
- ✓ TIBBIYOT FANLARI
- ✓ PEDAGOGIKA FANLARI

Bosh muharrir:

F.M.Muxtarov
t.f.b. PhD, dotsent

Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy
kommunikatsiya agentligida
2023-yil 3-mayda
№078777
raqam bilan ro'yxatga
olingan

Murojaat uchun

 [@fer_teach_uz](https://t.me/fer_teach_uz)
 +99893-343-13-14
 <https://fer-teach.uz/rai>

Mas'ul muharrir

S.I.Zokirov - f.-m.f.b. PhD., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

Taxrir hay'ati:

B.R.Ismailov – t.f.d., prof. MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

I.Byorno - Ph.D., Imeritus, Daniya Texnika Universiteti, Kopengagen, Daniya

L.K.Mamadaliyeva – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

M.E.Yunusaliyev – t.f.d. (DSc), prof. FarPI, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

X.B.Ismailov- t.f.n., dot., MAvezov Jan. Qoz. Univ-ti., Chimkent, Qozog'iston

J.T.Moldaliyev - bio. f. n., dotsent. OshDU, Osh, Qirg'iziston

T.M.Abdullayev – t.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

N.I.Ibrokhimov – f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

A.R.Nurmatov – tarix f.b. Ph.D., NamDU, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

D.F.To'xtasinov - ped.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

S.B.Atajonova - ped.f.b. Ph.D, AndMI, Andijon O'zbekiston

Sh.A.Umarov - f.-m.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

I.A.Rustamov - fal.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

B.X.Tolipov - f.f.b. Ph.D., TATU Farg'ona filiali, Farg'ona, O'zbekiston.

O.X.Otaqulov – t.f.n., dotsent. TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

O.S.Raimjonova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

R.A.Nurdinova – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

M.I.Ismoilov – t.f.b. Ph.D, dotsent, TATU Farg'ona filiali, O'zbekiston

I.T.Tojiboyev – t.f.n., dotsent, Farg'ona davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston

DIAGNOSIS AND INTENSIVE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES TO ACHIEVE THE TARGET LEVEL OF GLYCED HEMOGLOBIN AND REDUCE THE RISK OF VASCULAR COMPLICATIONS

Djurayeva Zilola Aramovna

*Samarkand State Medical University, Assistant of the Department of Endocrinology,
Scientific adviser*

Abduraximov Samariddin

Samarkand state Medical University

Akilov Bobir

Samarkand state Medical University

Bekmuratov Abbos

Samarkand state Medical University

Djalalova Ravza

Samarkand state Medical University

Annotation. *Control of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) requires multifactorial behavioral and pharmacological treatment to prevent the development or slow the progression of complications. The main characteristics of T2DM - hyperglycemia and insulin resistance in combination with oxidative stress, low-level inflammation, epigenetic changes, genetic predisposition, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, causing endothelial dysfunction, from the earliest stages are responsible for the metabolic environment that increases vascular risk in patients. Almost all patients with T2DM are at high and very high cardiovascular risk. The largest studies of the late 20th - early 21st centuries. demonstrated a significant reduction in intensive care complications early in the disease and a “legacy effect” with long-term historical significance of HbA1c control during their observational extensions. Reductions in HbA1c levels may also play a role in mediating the beneficial effects on cardiovascular risk observed with newer glucose-lowering drugs. The desires for glycemic control and organ-specific protection do not exclude, but complement each other. Reassessing individual glycemic goals and achieving them at regular intervals with early intensification of therapy is key to overcoming clinical inertia.*

KEYWORDS: *diabetes mellitus type 2; glycohemoglobin HbA1c; vascular complications; clinical inertia; Gliclazide MB*

ДИАГНОСТИКА И ИНТЕНСИВНОЕ ЛЕЧЕНИЕ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА 2 ТИПА ДЛЯ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ ЦЕЛЕВОГО УРОВНЯ ГЛИКИРОВАННОГО ГЕМОГЛОБИНА И СНИЖЕНИЯ РИСКА СОСУДИСТЫХ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ

Джураева Зилола Арамовна

*Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет, ассистент кафедры
эндокринологии, научный руководитель*

Абдурахимов Самариддин

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Акилов Бобир

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Бекмуратов Аббос

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Джалалова Равза

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

Аннотация. Контроль сахарного диабета 2 типа (СД2) требует многофакторного поведенческого и фармакологического лечения для предотвращения развития или замедления прогрессирования осложнений. Основные характеристики СД2 - гипергликемия и инсулинорезистентность в сочетании с окислительным стрессом, вялотекущим воспалением, эпигенетическими изменениями, генетической предрасположенностью, активацией ренин-ангиотензин-альдостероновой системы, вызывающей дисфункцию эндотелия, с самых ранних стадий ответственны за метаболические процессы. окружающей среды, которая увеличивает сосудистый риск у пациентов. Практически все пациенты с СД2 относятся к группе высокого и очень высокого сердечно-сосудистого риска. Крупнейшие исследования конца 20 - начала 21 веков. продемонстрировали значительное снижение осложнений интенсивной терапии на ранних стадиях заболевания и «наследственный эффект» с долгосрочной исторической значимостью контроля HbA1c во время их наблюдательного расширения. Снижение уровня HbA1c также может играть роль в обеспечении положительного влияния на сердечно-сосудистый риск, наблюдаемого при применении новых сахароснижающих препаратов. Стремление к гликемическому контролю и органоспецифической защите не исключают, а дополняют друг друга. Переоценка индивидуальных целей гликемии и их достижение через регулярные промежутки времени при ранней интенсификации терапии является ключом к преодолению клинической инерции.

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет 2 типа; гликогемоглобин HbA1c; сосудистые осложнения; клиническая инерция; Гликлазид МВ.

Introduction. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a heterogeneous disease with varying age of onset, degree of obesity, insulin resistance, and tendency to develop complications. Maintaining normal glucose homeostasis is determined by a high degree of interaction between the liver, muscles, adipocytes, pancreas, kidneys and the neuroendocrine system, ensuring a stable level of glycemia [1]. Control of T2DM involves multifactorial behavioral and pharmacological treatment to prevent the development or slow the progression of complications and maintain quality of life. Synergistic effects on multiple pathophysiological mechanisms, potentially leading to long-term therapeutic efficacy without increasing the risk of adverse events, are important for successful therapy. Hyperglycemia and insulin resistance - the main characteristics of T2DM - in combination with oxidative stress, low-level inflammation, epigenetic changes, genetic predisposition, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, causing endothelial dysfunction, from the earliest stages are responsible for the metabolic environment that increases vascular risk in patients [2]. The organic interaction between the microvasculature and resident tissue cells becomes dysfunctional under the influence of these factors. Microvascular dysfunction in diabetes precedes anatomical microvascular complications in the heart, brain, blood vessels, kidney, retina, nervous tissue, muscles and other organs. The assumption of the reversibility of microvascular damage with concomitant dysfunction in the early stages of the disease, provided adequate interventions, is substantiated. Unfortunately, even when diagnosing T2DM, vascular pathology is detected - up to 50% of cases [3]. Moreover, according to the UK Biobank, with a median follow-up of 11 years, the risk of developing such clinical outcomes as chronic kidney disease (CKD), chronic heart failure (CHF), atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) increases gradiently even in people with prediabetes , according to glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) indicators, which do not yet have diagnostic values for T2DM [4]. According to the European Society of Cardiology (European Society of Cardiology), almost all patients with T2DM and type 1 diabetes (T1DM) over 40 years of age are at high and very high cardiovascular risk [5]. How should patients with diabetes be treated from the onset of the disease and what indicators should be followed? The cornerstone in assessing the effect of glycemic control on the development of complications in patients with T1DM during intensive treatment was laid by the DCCT (Diabetes Control and Complications Trial) study [6]. The DCCT study (mean glycated hemoglobin HbA1c level ~7% (53 mmol/mol)) showed a reduction in the development and progression of early microvascular and neurological

complications associated with diabetes, by 34–76% compared to the traditional treatment group (HbA1c at ~9% (75 mmol/mol)) for an average of 6.5 years of therapy. Intensive therapy was associated with weight gain and a threefold increase in the risk of hypoglycemia. At the end of DCCT, a long-term observational study, EDIC (Epidemiology of Diabetes Interventions and Complications study), was initiated. Despite the convergence of HbA1c levels between the two groups, the development and progression of complications was still significantly less in the intensive treatment group compared with the conventional treatment group; this phenomenon has been called "metabolic memory". The DCCT trial demonstrated a significant reduction in early complications with intensive care, and the phenomenon of metabolic memory during the EDIC period contributed to a significant reduction in the burden of complications over time—a 57% risk of cardiovascular events and a 33% mortality rate in the intensive treatment group compared with traditional treatment group [6]. Follow-up up to 29 years identified HbA1c as the strongest modifiable risk factor for a first cardiovascular event (RR 1.38; 95% CI 1.21–1.56 per 1% HbA1c); serious cardiovascular event (MACE) - non-fatal myocardial infarction (MI), non-fatal stroke, cardiovascular death (RR 1.54; 95% CI 1.30–1.82) [7]. In T2DM, the importance of early targeting (from the onset of the disease) on glycemic control to prevent complications was shown in the UKPDS (United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study) study [8, 9]. This research, initiated almost 50 years ago when routine therapeutic interventions of today were not yet available (eg, the use of statins), has had a tremendous impact on the practice of treating T2DM. The UKPDS study, initiated in 1977 at the John Radcliffe Hospital in Oxford (UK), had three stages: the first - from 1977 to 1997. (almost 43,000 patient-years of observation), the second - from 1997 to 2007. (67,000 patient-years), the third - from 2001 to 2021. (78,000 patient-years). In summary, a 44-year follow-up period has now been reached, and data are available on the long-term effects of intensive glycemic control in T2DM. A total of 4209 people (23 clinical sites) with newly diagnosed T2DM, mostly white men, were randomized at baseline. The effect of intensive glycemic control with either insulin or sulfonylureas (metformin in overweight patients) was studied compared with traditional therapy. Diabetes complications, diabetes-related mortality, and all-cause mortality were recorded. The results of the first period of UKPDS are well known and have formed the basis of the global concept of treatment of T2DM: intensive glycemic control reduced the risk of all diabetes-related endpoints, microvascular complications, MI and all-cause mortality. And

treatment with metformin was associated with a greater reduction in risk, making the drug a first-line treatment for many years. Although the glycemic differences between the intensive control and usual care groups disappeared soon after the end of the study, the benefits of the former were maintained during the observation period. However, UKPDS continues to be a source of data influencing the global concept of T2DM treatment. The main question after 44 years of UKPDS research, highlighted at the 2022 EASD Congress, is whether there is a “legacy effect”, i.e. Does the effect of strict glucose control persist after the end of the initial active phase of the trial? First identified in the 30-year UKPDS analysis [10], this effect remains virtually unchanged up to 44 years of follow-up. Data were presented for all endpoints related to diabetes, MI, microvascular complications, and all-cause mortality. In the sulfonylurea/insulin group compared with conventional therapy, the relative risk reduction after 44 years was 10, 15, 26 and 11%, respectively, and for metformin compared with conventional therapy the corresponding figures were: 19, 31, 10 and 25% [11]. . These significant results highlight the critical importance of identifying and aggressively treating T2DM “at the earliest opportunity.” One of the study coordinators, Professor Ruri Holman, when explaining the “legacy effect”, emphasized the long-term historical importance of HbA1c control, as a potential increase in all-cause mortality was identified for a 1% increase in HbA1c levels (Figure 1). Prof. R. Holman suggested that the “legacy effect” is essentially a protection against hyperglycemia, which activates oxidative stress, the formation of proteins, advanced glycation end products, and epigenetic changes leading to the effects of inflammatory proteins. He added that the larger size of metformin's "legacy" effect suggests that additional drug-related protective mechanisms, such as inhibition of inflammatory pathways, may be at play. Later N. Laiteerapong et al. [12] determined the effect of delayed glycemic control in a cohort study of 34,737 patients with newly diagnosed T2DM. The authors examined the associations between HbA1c 9.0% (>75 mmol/mol) and various periods of early exposure (0–1, 0–2, 0–3, 0–4, 0–5, 0–6, and 0–7 years), the incidence of micro- and macrovascular complications and mortality in these patients with an average follow-up of 13 years. Compared with HbA1c 6.5% (>48 mmol/mol) was associated with more frequent micro- and macrovascular events, and HbA1c >7.0% (>53 mmol/mol) was associated with increased mortality. These results support the idea that immediate treatment, aimed at careful and long-term glycemic control immediately after diagnosis, necessary to prevent the long-term risk of diabetes complications and increased mortality. The significance of the

first UKPDS results for the scientific community and practical medicine is illustrated by the fact that after their presentation, a whole cascade of multicenter studies on similar issues was launched. In order to evaluate the protective role of effective glycemic control to prevent fatal and non-fatal cardiovascular events in patients with T2DM, but with a long history of the disease and high cardiovascular risk, several large-scale prospective studies with a similar design were initiated almost simultaneously - ACCORD (Action to Control Cardiovascular Risk in Diabetes), VADT (Veterans Affairs Diabetes Trial) and ADVANCE (Action in Diabetes and Vascular Disease: Preterax and Diamicron Modified Release Controlled Evaluation) [13–15]. The ACCORD and VADT trials used a strategy of rapid intensification of therapy with the introduction regimens of multiple oral antihyperglycemic agents and insulin, whereas the ADVANCE trial used a much more cautious escalation strategy with the original gliclazide MB (Diabeton MB®) and other drugs, resulting in a much faster reduction in HbA1c (within 3–6 months) in ACCORD and VADT compared with 2 years in the ADVANCE study. This resulted in significant weight gain in patients in the intensive glycemic control groups in the ACCORD (3.5 kg) and VADT (8.4 kg) studies, but not in the ADVANCE study (0.1 kg). In addition, the incidence of severe hypoglycemia in the ACCORD and VADT studies was 6 times higher than in the ADVANCE study.

Conclusion. We can conclude that the second decade of the 21st century. has already become routinely characterized as a time of paradigm shift in the treatment of T2DM. The cardio-reno-metabolic approach and the expansion of NGLT-2 drugs into other areas of medicine (primarily cardiology and nephrology) open up promising prospects for improving the prognosis of patients. At the same time, the above data on the importance of early achievement of target glycemic control emphasize that in T2DM, it is the combination of approaches that provides maximum benefits for patients: providing organ protection with glucose-lowering drugs with proven properties to influence outcomes and prognosis, as well as achieving adequate glycemic control throughout the course of the disease (the duration of which is often measured over several decades), with the inevitable need to both overcome clinical inertia and take into account the dynamically changing individual characteristics of the status of a particular patient.

References:

1. Отамуродов УГ угли, Абдужамбилов АН угли, Сабирова ДШ. Гипертиреоз. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(5):134-139.

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

2. Шухратовна СД, Рустамовна РГ, Нодир Р. Изменения уровня хГ в системе мать-плацента-плод прирезус несовместимой беременности. *Достижения науки и образования*. 2020;(10 (64)):91-93.
3. Хамраев Х, Содиков С, Хамраева Д, Собирова Д. Клинико-функциональное состояние печени у больных с сахарным диабетом. *ЖПБМ*. 2018;(1 (99)):189-191
4. Даминов АТ, Хакбердиева В, Жаникулов С, Муродхонов С. Клинический случай первичный гипотиреоз. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):131-134.
5. Shukhratovna SD, Suratovich OF. Морфологические особенности коры надпочечников потомства крыс в онтогенезе в условиях внутриутробного воздействия пестицидов через организм матери (обзорная статья). *Journal of biomedicine and practice*. 2023;8(4). Accessed January 12, 2024. <https://tadqiqot.uz/index.php/biomedicine/article/view/8217>
6. Мизамова МАК, Эшпулатова ГНК, Эшмуродова ЗНК, Салимова ДЭ. Осложнения акромегалии, связанные со здоровьем, текущие и перспективные варианты лечения. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):187-195.
7. Нарбаев А, Джураева З, Курбонова Н, Кувондииков Г, Давранова А, Содиков С. Особенности изучения многофакторного управления сахарным диабетом 2 типа. *Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины*. 2017;(4 (97)):78-79.
8. Ибрагимов УС, Туракулов ЖТУ, Гуломов ШНУ, Салимова ДЭ. Просвещение пациентов: Гипогликемия (низкий уровень глюкозы в крови) у людей с диабетом. *ScienceandEducation*. 2023;4(4):226-233.
9. Содиков С, Каримова Н, Каримова З. Реабилитация больных пожилого возраста сахарным диабетом 2-типа. *ЖПБМ*. 2017;(4 (97)):105-106.
10. Хамидова МН, Исмадова ИФ, Бердиев ЖШ, Негматова ГШ, Даминов АТ. Сахарный диабети COVID-19. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*. 2022;2(13):190-204.
11. Шухратовна СД, Кахрамонович ЮУ, Махмудович КТ. Структурные изменения сосудисто-стромального комплекса щитовидной железы при эутиреоидной и токсических формах зоба. *Научный журнал*. 2019;(10 (44)):67-69.
12. Собиржонова КН, Саллохидинович СС, Акбаровна ОМ.

- Эпидемиологический Статус И Факторы Риска Сахарного Диабета На Сегодняшний День. *MiastoPrzyszłości*. 2023;32:212-219.
13. Salimova DE, Daminov AT. A clinical case based on the experience of treating hypertension in a patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity and vitamin d deficiency. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023;2(12):150-154.
14. Takhirovich DA. Assessment of hearing function in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(9):124-126.
15. Qahramonov FA, Amirov BY, Tursunboyeva LI, Daminov AT. Autoimmuntireoiditbilankasallanganbemorlardagifunksionalbuzilishlarningdifferensialdiagnostikasidaqalqonsimonbezzichliginianiqlash. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3):82-86.
16. Nazira K, Siddikovna TG, Davranovna DA, Takhirovich DA, Tulkinovich OS. Cardiovascular complications in patients who have had covid on the background of diabetes mellitus 2.1. 2021;2(3):37-41.
17. Choriyev S, Gadoeva Z, Mardonova F, Jurakulov F, Hafizov S, Daminov AT. Changes in the thyroid gland in the long period after a new coronavirus infection. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(12):102-106.
18. Kamalov T, Bahriev N, Yuldashev U, Sabirova D. Clinical and hormonal characteristics of primary hypogonadism in preschool boys. *MedFarm*. 2019;10(9). doi:10.32743/2658-4093.2019.9.10.188
19. Daminov AT, Yuldoshev B, Murodullo I, Naimova N. Clinical case of primary hypothyroidism. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 special):135-138.
20. Daminov A, Khaydarov O, Hasanova M, Abdukakhorova R. Complications of glucocorticoid therapy in patients diabetes survived COVID-19. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*. 2023;3(4):197-200.
21. Takhirovich DA, Corners SJA, Shukhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SG, Zaynuddinovna MG. Course of COVID-19 in patients with diabetes mellitus. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*. 2022;3(02):73-76. doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/B6FU2

22. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, Suxrobovna XM, Ikromovna AZ. Diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. *Pedagog.* 2022;5(5):381-386.
23. O'g'li SOS, O'g'li RSO, Taxirovich DA. Diffuz toksik buqoq. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования.* 2023;4(1):131-133.
24. Negmatova GS, Toshimova GT qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Effectiveness of correction of dyslipidemia in elderly patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 SPECIAL):269-274.
25. G.Sh N, D.e S, Oybekovma XS, Qamariddinovna XA, O'g'li BJA. Endocrine glands, structure, age features, functions. *PEDAGOG.* 2022;5(5):341-345.
26. Sobirjonovna KN. Factors determining the clinical significance of depeptidyl peptidase 4 inhibitors in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World Bulletin of Public Health.* 2022;8:67-72.
27. Daminov AT, Djabbarova D, Abduvohidova N, Furkatova D, Farxodova S, Ibragimova P. Features of bone tissue remodeling in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Science and Education.* 2023;4(11).
28. Daminov Abdurasul Takhirovich RSU. Features of the clinic, rehabilitation, treatment of autoimmune thyroiditis in the conditions of the iodine-deficiency region. Published online April 12, 2023. doi:10.5281/ZENODO.7820412
29. Shuhratovna NG, Shukhratovna SD. Features of the course of autoimmune hepatitis in children as a variant of autoimmune polyglandular syndrome. *Asia Journ of Multidimensi Resear (AJMR).* 2020;9(7):89. doi:10.5958/2278-4853.2020.00228.1
30. Erkinovna SD. Features of the Course of Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 with Arterial Hypertension. *JournalNX.* Published online 2020:460-461.
31. Negmatova GS, Xakimova GD qizi, Abdiyev LS o'g'li, Daminov AT. Features of the rules for insulin injection techniques in elderly and senile patients with diabetes mellitus. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences.* 2024;3(1 special):259-264.
32. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Features of type 1 diabetes in children who have COVID-19. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149).* 2023;1(9):121-123.
33. Xudoyorov S, Mirkomilova M, Burxonov U, Sayfiyeva G, Sheralieva N, Daminov AT. Fourniers gangrene in modern conditions. *Science and Education.*

2023;4(12):107-117.

34. Alimovna KN, Sobirjanovna KN, Abdurasul D, Tulkinovich OS. Growth hormone for the treatment of hereditary diseases in children. 10.
35. Negmatova .G.Sh, D.e S, Qizi MZO, Mannobovich MS, Orifjonovich MM. HERPETIC MENINGITIS. *PEDAGOG*. 2022;5(5):346-348.
36. Ahrorbek N, Myungjae L, Jungjae L, et al. Hormonal Regulation. *Texa Jour of Mutl Stud*. 2023;25:39-43.
37. Ismoilova SI. Impact of vitamin D deficiency on the risk of developing type 1 diabetes. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(3).
38. T DA, Umidbekovna UM, Muhitdinovna KN. Methodology of Using Modern Graphics Programs in Teaching Engineering Graphics. 1. Published online December 8, 2023:158-162.
39. Sabirjanovna KN, Takhirovich DA, Jahongir D, Najmiddin X, Samandar G, Mehrangiz X. Negative Impact of Covid-19 on the Endocrine System. *American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149)*. 2023;1(8):148-153.
40. Takhirovich DA, Zafarovna KM, Isroilovna IS. Nevrologiyada endokrin o`zgarishlar. *so`ngi ilmiy tadqiqotlar nazariyasi*. 2023;6(12):417-422.
41. Negmatova GS, Salimova DE. Qandli diabet 2-tipning arterial gipertenziyabilan birgalikdakechish xususiyatlarivaularnidavolashusullari. *Science and Education*. 2023;4(2):516-519.
42. Taxirovich DA, J T, O E, I A. Qandli diabet-2 tipi bor bemorlarda covid-19 kasalligini glukokortikoidlar bilan davolash dinamikasini baholash. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. 2023;34:78-81.
43. G.Sh N, D.e S, Alisherovich BA, Erkin R is the son of S, Bektash U is the son of S. Relationship between diabetic nephropathy and cardiac disorders in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(5):337-340.
44. Daminov AT, Sa`dullayeva SM qizi, Ismoilova SI qizi. Samarqand viloyatida qandli diabet asoratlari uchrash chastotasi. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2024;3(3 SPECIAL):139-142.
45. Shukhratovna NG, Erkinovna SD, O`g`li IBI, Qizi ADD. The role of gastrointestinal hormones in the pathology of the digestive system. *Pedagog*. 2022;5(6):408-412.

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 04. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 04. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 04. | 2024

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tahririyat manzili:

150100, Farg‘ona vil., Farg‘ona sh., Solim ko‘chasi, 23/4-uy, 26-xonadon

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Bizning web-sahifa:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

“Tadqiq va tatbiq” ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali "Fer-Teach" MChJ muassisligida tashkil etilgan bo‘lib, ilmiy va uslubiy jihatdan Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Farg‘ona filiali tomonidan qo‘llab-quvvatlanadi. Mazkur jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan 2023-yil 3-mayda ommaviy axborot vositasi sifatida davlat ro‘yxatidan (№ 078777) o‘tkazilgan.

ISSN 3030-3362.

Jurnal aniq va tabiiy fanlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy fanlar, texnika fanlari, tibbiyot fanlari, pedagogika fanlari sohalarini qamrab oladi. Tahrir hay‘ati a‘zolidan respublikaning turli OTMlarida faoliyat olib boruvchi fan nomzodlari va doktorlari o‘rin olishgan..

Nashr tillari: O‘zbek, Rus, Ingliz va Qoraqalpoq tillari

Tadqiq va tatbiq ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal	Research and implementation scientific-methodical journal	Исследования и внедрение научно-методический журнал
Tom 02. Son. 04. 2024	Vol. 02. Iss. 04. 2024	Том 02. Вып. 04. 2024

Научно-методический журнал “ Исследования и внедрение ”

Адрес редакции:

150100, Ферганская область, г. Фергана, улица Солим, дом 23/4, кв. 26

Е-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Наш сайт:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

Учредителем научно-технического журнала

«Исследования и внедрение» является ООО “Fer-Teach”.

Журнал издается с 2023 года, зарегистрирован 3 мая 2023 года Агентством информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан (Сертификат № 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

«Исследования и внедрение» является специализированным журналом в области техники и охватывает все основные направления исследований и разработок в различных областях технических наук: физике, математике, информационных технологиях. В журнале также публикуются научные статьи по лингвистике, методике преподавания и истории развития технических наук.

Языки издания: Узбекский, русский, английский и каракалпакский

Tadqiq va tatbiq
ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal

Tom 02. | Son. 04. | 2024

Research and implementation
scientific-methodical journal

Vol. 02. | Iss. 04. | 2024

Исследования и внедрение
научно-методический журнал

Том 02. | Вып. 04. | 2024

Scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation”

Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, building 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@fer-teach.uz

Our website:

<https://fer-teach.uz/>

The scientific and methodological journal “Research and implementation” was founded by Fer-Teach LLC and supported by the Fergana branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi. This journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2023 (No 078777).

ISSN 3030-3362.

"Research and implementation" is a specialized journal in the field of technology and covers all major areas of research and development in various fields of technical sciences: physics, mathematics, information technology. The journal also publishes scientific articles on linguistics, teaching methods and the history of the development of technical sciences.

Languages: Uzbek, Russian, English, Karakalpak

ВНИМАНИЕ!

При использовании материалов журнала необходимо указывать источник. Авторы статей несут ответственность за содержание статей и за сам факт их публикации.

Редакция не всегда разделяет мнения авторов и не несет ответственности за недостоверность публикуемых данных.

Редакция журнала не несет никакой ответственности перед авторами и/или третьими лицами и организациями за возможный ущерб, вызванный публикацией статьи.

ATTENTION!

When using journal materials, you must indicate the source.

The authors of the articles are responsible for the content of the articles and for the very fact of their publication.

The editors do not always share the opinions of the authors and are not responsible for the unreliability of the published data.

The editorial board of the journal does not bear any responsibility to the authors and / or third parties and organizations for possible damage caused by the publication of the article

DIQQAT!

Jurnal materiallaridan foydalanganda manbani ko'rsatish kerak.

Maqola mualliflari maqolalar mazmuni va ularning nashr etilishi fakti uchun javobgardirlar.

Har doim ham mualliflarning fikrlari tahririyat nuqtai nazarini ifodalamaydi va nashr etilgan ma'lumotlarning haqiqiyligi uchun javobgar emas.

Jurnal tahririyati mualliflar va/yoki uchinchi shaxslar va tashkilotlarga maqolaning e'lon qilinishi natijasida yetkazilishi mumkin bo'lgan zarar uchun javobgar emas.